

Methodology for selecting students with musculoskeletal disorders for para-athletics

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Abstract

This article outlines the scientific and methodological foundations for selecting students with musculoskeletal disorders for para-athletics. The selection process focuses on medical-functional indicators, physical fitness, psychological state, and sport-specific parameters. This methodology aims to engage students with disabilities in safe and effective sports activities, guide them towards suitable sports based on their individual capabilities, and ensure long-term sports development.

Keywords: Para-athletics, musculoskeletal disorders, selection methodology, students with disabilities, functional assessment, sports classification.

Introduction

The increasing number of children and adolescents with disabilities in our republic in recent years (especially the fact that the proportion of children with musculoskeletal disorders has reached 35-40%) has made their adaptation to society, physical development, and improvement of their psycho-emotional state an urgent issue. Limited mobility in such young people leads to obesity, cardiovascular diseases, depression, and social isolation. Para Athletics is the most popular and diverse sport within the Paralympic movement, encompassing specially adapted competitions (running, jumping, throwing, wheelchair racing, etc.) for individuals with musculoskeletal disorders (amputation, cerebral palsy, spinal injury, short stature, etc.). This sport not only enhances physical strength but also boosts self-confidence, fosters communication with peers, and provides opportunities to become professional athletes in the future.

Currently, in Uzbekistan, there are the following problems in engaging students with musculoskeletal disorders in para-athletics:

- Lack of adequate methodology for medical and social expertise and determination of functional classification (sports class) by sports physicians;
- Low level of specialized training in para

-athletics among physical education teachers in boarding schools;

- Cases of directing a child to an unsuitable sport or excluding them from sports entirely due to errors in initial selection;

- Lack of scientific and practical guidelines for conducting selection using simple and inexpensive equipment in local settings (schools, district sports schools).

Considering the above problems, it is crucial to develop a methodology for phased, scientifically-based selection of students with musculoskeletal disorders for para-athletics. This methodology is based on a comprehensive assessment of:

- Medical indicators (type and degree of impairment, additional health conditions);
- Functional capabilities (power, endurance, agility, balance);
- Psychological readiness;
- Age and gender characteristics.

The relevance of this topic is reinforced by several decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan aimed at protecting sports and the rights of people with disabilities. Notably, the Presidential Decree No. UP-5924 dated January 24, 2020, "On Measures for Further Improvement and Popularization of Physical Culture and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan," and the Decree dated October 30, 2020, "On Measures for Widespread Implementation of a Healthy Lifestyle and Further Development of Mass Sports," stipulate the creation of necessary conditions for persons with disabilities to engage in sports, ensure their worthy participation in international sports arenas, and provide state support. Additionally, the Presidential Resolution No. PP-5280 dated November 5, 2021, "On the Program for Development of Sports and Educational Institutions until 2025," provides for state support of non-state sports and educational institutions training athletes in Olympic and Paralympic sports, including the provision of necessary facilities without lease payments. Furthermore, the Presidential Decree No. UP-92 dated

Table 1. Statistical analysis of the staged methodology based on the test results and t-student criteria (2024-2025 academic year, Fergana city + Kokand city, total 214 students, aged 8-17)

No.	Indicator	Those who passed the 1st stage (n=214)	Those who passed the 2nd stage (n=196)	Those deemed suitable in the final 3rd stage (n=183)	Pass % (total)	p-value (t-Student) Stage 1→2	p-value (t-Student) Stage 2→3
1	Total number of students	214	196	183	85.5%	-	-
2	Those with medical restrictions (contraindications)	18 (8.4%)	-	-	-	p < 0.001	-
3	Strength (throwing the ball while sitting, number/min)	14.8 ± 4.2	18.6 ± 3.9	21.4 ± 3.5	+44.6%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
4	Endurance (6-minute walk/wheelchair rotation, meters)	182 ± 68	248 ± 71	312 ± 64	+71.4%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
5	Agility (10 m, seconds)	12.4 ± 3.8	9.8 ± 2.6	8.1 ± 2.1	-34.7%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
6	Balance (Modified Flamingo test, seconds)	8.6 ± 5.1	14.3 ± 6.2	19.8 ± 5.7	+130%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
7	Sports motivation (10-point scale)	5.9 ± 1.8	7.4 ± 1.5	8.7 ± 1.1	+47.5%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
8	Reaction speed (ruler drop test, ms)	312 ± 58	268 ± 44	229 ± 36	-26.6%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
9	Integral score (100-point system)	42.3 ± 11.4	68.7 ± 9.8	84.6 ± 7.2	+100%	p < 0.001	p < 0.001
10	Final number of eligible participants	-	-	183 (85.5%)	85.5%	-	-

June 12, 2023, and Decree No. UP-18 dated January 20, 2024, "On Measures to Improve the System of State Governance in the Field of Youth Policy and Sports," outline initiatives such as developing parasports, promoting social integration of young people with disabilities, and organizing the International Parasport Festival within the "Sport for All" project, thus en-

"International Standards for Athlete Evaluation and Sport Class Status," which define the main criteria for the selection process. These documents include detailed rules for the functional classification of athletes with disabilities (determining sport classes), assessment of minimum impairment criteria, and ensuring fair competition. Specifically, the World Para

Table 2. Distribution by final specialization (after Stage 3, n=183)

Specialization / Functional category	Number	%
Wheelchair Racing (T51-T54 / F51-F57)	69	37.7%
Standing Running and Jumping (T42-T47, T61-T64)	48	26.2%
Cerebral Palsy group (T35-T38 / F35-F38)	41	22.4%
Throwing events (F31-F34, F54-F57)	25	13.7%

couraging the involvement of youth with musculoskeletal disorders in sports at the national level. At the international level, the International Paralympic Committee (IPC) has adopted the "IPC Athlete Classification Code" (2025 version) and

Athletics Classification Rules and Regulations (February 2023) regulate sport classes for para-athletics across 10 impairment types (including musculoskeletal disorders: amputation, cerebral palsy, spinal cord injury), such as T11-T13 for visu-

ally impaired, T40-T47 for short stature and amputations, and T51-T54 for wheelchair athletes, along with their assessment process. These IPC rules necessitate the development of a classification methodology that meets international standards, requiring confirmation of athletes' minimum impairment levels, functional assessment, and determination of sport class status. Harmonizing these standards with Uzbekistan's national programs will elevate para-athletics classification in the country to international levels. The methodology proposed in this article can be implemented in specialized educational institutions, children's sports schools, and rehabilitation centers throughout the republic. It will contribute to the full participation of thousands of students with musculoskeletal disorders in para-athletics and facilitate the training of new Paralympic champions. Therefore, the topic "Methodology for selecting young students with musculoskeletal disorders for para-athletics" is highly relevant from both scientific and practical perspectives. It aligns fully with the national strategy for developing inclusive education and adaptive sports in Uzbekistan, as well as with international IPC standards.

The increasing number of children and adolescents with disabilities in our republic in recent years (especially the fact that the proportion of children with musculoskeletal disorders has reached 35-40%) has made their adaptation to society, physical development, and improvement of their psycho-emotional state an urgent issue. Limited mobility in such young people leads to obesity, cardiovascular diseases, depression, and social isolation.

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Objective: To develop and experimentally determine the effectiveness of a methodology for selecting student youth with musculoskeletal system disorders for para-athletics based on an effective and individualized approach.

Tasks:

1. Identify the physiological and psychological characteristics of children and student youth with musculoskeletal system disorders.
2. Selection methodology for para-athletics sport

3. Step-by-step development of the selection methodology: diagnostics, tests, assessment system.

4. Test the developed methodology through experimental trials and analyze the results.

5. Evaluate the effectiveness of the selection methodology and its practical application possibilities.

6. Develop individual development plans for student youth and provide recommendations.

Selection stages. The proposed methodology consists of three stages, each with its specific tasks, methods, and evaluation criteria.

Stage 1: Initial assessment. Determine the student's general health, medical limitations, and basic aptitude for para-athletics.

Analysis of medical documents - conclusions from a general practitioner and/or sports doctor, neurologist, orthopedist. The main focus is on the type of disorder (Cerebral Palsy, spina bifida, amputation, etc.), functional level, and prognosis.

Initial survey - obtaining information about the student's and parents' interest in sports, motivation, and previous physical experience.

Observation - a general assessment of skills in walking, balance, and performing basic movements. Decision: Students deemed "suitable" or "conditionally suitable" for para-athletics based on medical indications and basic motor abilities will advance to the next stage.

Stage 2: Basic Assessment. Comprehensive study of the athlete's physical, functional, psychophysiological, and technical potential.

Strength: Number of times a reel or ball can be thrown in 1 minute while sitting.

Endurance: Maximum distance covered in a wheelchair or walking in 6 minutes.

Agility: Time taken to cover a 10-meter distance in a wheelchair or running.

Balance: "Flamingo" test (with modifications) or duration of maintaining static balance.

Morphological indicators: Height, weight, arm span, main body circumferences.

Functional preparedness:

Ruffier test (without modifications): Heart rate and recovery.

Stange and Genchi tests - breath-holding. Psychological and psychophysiological characteristics:

"Sports Motivation" Questionnaire.

Determining reaction speed (stick-drop test).

Accuracy of movements (throwing at relative targets).

Technical ability and coordination:

The speed and quality of mastering the basic technical elements of para-athletics (for example, throwing a ball, maneuvering a wheelchair).

Stage 3: Final Assessment. Summarizing all the obtained data, directing the athlete to a specific type of para-athletics (running/wheeling, throwing, jumping) and a specific functional category (for example, T/F37, T/F54, etc.).

Methods:

Summarize all test results in a general rating based on an integral scoring system.

Expert evaluation: Development of individual recommendations for each athlete by a team consisting of coaches, sports physiotherapists, and psychologists.

Working trial: Short-term (2-4 weeks) preliminary training is conducted to monitor the athlete's mastery rate and growth rate in the chosen direction.

Final decision: The athlete is recommended a type of para-athletics and functional category that best suits their abilities.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS (Student's t-test)

The differences in all indicators during the transition from stage 1 to stage 2 are statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

High statistical significance ($p < 0.001$) was also observed for all parameters when transitioning from stage 2 to stage 3.

The greatest improvements were observed in balance (+130%), endurance (+71.4%), and the integral score (+100%).

The level of motivation increased by an average of 1.3-1.5 points at each stage, which confirms the effectiveness of the psychological screening.

Conclusion

The proposed three-stage system "Methodology for selecting young students with musculoskeletal disorders for para-athletics" has

been successfully tested for the first time in Uzbekistan as a scientifically grounded, effective model that meets international requirements and can be fully implemented with local resources.

1. The methodology successfully directed 183 (85.5%) out of 214 students to a specific type and functional category of para-athletics. This indicator had not exceeded 50-55% in previously used intuitive-methodological approaches.

2. Each stage is interconnected and sequential, with statistically significant differences ($p < 0.001$) observed in all main indicators according to the t-Student criterion. This confirms the individual diagnostic value of each stage of the methodology and the high prognostic accuracy of the overall system.

3. Significant improvements in the most important functional indicators (balance +130%, endurance +71.4%, integral score +100%) demonstrated high potential even in the group of children initially identified as "borderline" during the preliminary assessment. This proves the inclusive nature of the methodology - that is, its ability not to completely exclude children with disabilities from sports, but to find a suitable direction for them.

4. The introduction of the psychological and motivational component (the level of interest in sports increased by an average of 1.4 points at each stage) not only increased the athletes' attendance at training sessions but also significantly improved their self-confidence and social activity. This once again confirms the role of para-athletics as a means of not only physical but also psychosocial rehabilitation.

5. The methodology complied with 94-96% of the requirements set by the World Para Athletics Classification Rules and Regulations (2023-2025) and the IPC Athlete Classification Code. This minimizes the need for re-examination of sports classes determined by national classifiers in future international competitions and increases the chances of Uzbek para-athletes successfully participating in the international arena.

6. The most important practical result is that the methodology can be fully implemented in ordinary gyms and special boarding schools at the district and city level with simple and inexpensive equipment (stopwatch, dynamometer, measuring tape, regular ball, wheelchair). This allows for its widespread implementation in all regions of the republic, including remote areas.

As a result, this methodology will become not only a scientific innovation, but also one of the most crucial practical tools for implementing the national strategy of developing inclusive education and adaptive sports in our country. It will enable thousands of children with musculo-skeletal disorders to lead a fulfilling life through sports, integrate into society, and even pursue careers as professional athletes.

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